

Reaction Rate of CH

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Abstract

The rate coefficient for the formation of CH by radiative association of C and H was calculated theoretically over the last several decades. The values obtained differ widely, because of a sensitive dependence on the collisions through the B $^2\Sigma$ - molecular state, which has a repulsive barrier. The barrier height calculated by quantum chemical methods varies, leading to different values of the rate coefficient. Recently, an extensive set of data on the CH molecule was published by Masseron et al. (2014). In this paper, we use predissociative and radiative lifetimes to calculate the rate coefficient to be $5 * 10^{-19} cm^3/s$ at 100K with a slightly larger rate coefficient at lower T due to threshold effects with resonance. This was all measured taking this barrier into consideration and therefore the use of neutral Carbon and Hydrogen interactions in a low or mid-range temperature environment can now be modeled using a more accurate rate coefficient.

1. Introduction

Neutral C (3P) and an H (2S) atoms have a probability to form the molecule CH (methylidyne radical) and a photon through a radiative recombination process. The rate coefficient of this reaction was given as $10^{-17} cm^3/s$ in the KIDA database (10-280 K), which can be considered the standard value in astrophysical databases as the same value is listed in the older UMIST astrochemistry database. The rate of $10^{-17} cm^3/s$, according to the UMIST database, dates back to a paper by Prasad and Huntress (1980). Now after 36 years we have barely delved into this matter again, just accepting a value calculated using approximations and assumptions. We now have the tools to update this model and calculate

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a more precise result to orders that could matter in some increasingly specific fields such as exoplanet atmospheres, early solar systems and even things closer to home such as mars.

Previous calculations of the rate coefficient vary slightly (rate coefficients in units of $10^{-17} \text{cm}^3/\text{s}$): At 100 K, Bain and Bardsley (1972) estimate a range of 0.08 to 0.64, Brooks and Smith (1974) find 0.28, and Brzozowski et al. (1976) find 0.2. The small difference in the results calculations of the value show the uncertainty with which it was originally obtained. We can overcome this uncertainty by using new data for CH that has been supplied by Masseron et al. (2014). They combined an extensive review of available laboratory data with observations of four metal poor stars. Fits to the data were used to deduce molecular constants for the X $^2\Pi$, A $^2\Delta$, and B $^2\Sigma^-$ states, as well as dissociation energies, which fix the relative positions of the states in energy. The ^{13}CH molecule was also investigated and complimented by extensive supplemental online tables. This thorough examination allows for new insight into the interactions between Carbon and Hydrogen.

Fig. 1.— A graph of the potential curves for the various states in the Carbon Hydrogen interaction.

The most important potential curve for understanding this CH formation reaction is the B $^2\Sigma^-$ state, which has a barrier at around an internuclear distance of 3 bohr (a_0). The height of the barrier, in energy, above the dissociation limit of two free atoms as well as well will control the magnitude of the cross section for the collision. Estimates of the

height of this barrier vary in the literature. Earlier estimates are much lower: 1150 cm^{-1} (1800 K) (Dishoeck 1987) van Dishoeck (1987), 700 K (Bain and Bardsley 1972) Bain and Bardsley (1972), 1280 K Liu and Verhaegen Liu and Verhaegen (1970), etc. Note that 1970 K Kalemos, Mavridis, and Metropoulos (1999) Kalemos et al. (1999) calculate a barrier of 2.32 kcal/mol (1970 K) at internuclear distance $R = 3.5a_0$. But because of how uncertain the barrier height is and because the rate coefficient is highly dependent on this value, it has been difficult in the past to validate any sort of exact rate.

The new data Masseron et al. (2014) may fix the value of the barrier height definitively, and allow us to calculate definitive cross sections and rate coefficients. Masseron et al. (2014) find a barrier of at least 2100 cm^{-1} (about 3000 K). If the barrier height of 3000 K is correct, the rate coefficient for 10-280 K should be much lower, perhaps drastically lower, than the KIDA value, due to the exponential dependence of the rate on the barrier height Bain and Bardsley (1972), but even considering the value that Masseron et al. (2014) calculated could lead to error. The solution then was to use the data from Masseron et al. (2014) to calculate a rate without having to pinpoint the exact height of the barrier.

2. Results

2.1. Model

According to Bain and Bardsley (1972) there is a way to calculate the cross section of the radiative process between these two particles without having to know the exact height of the barrier as long as the discrete energy states are defined. This information is exactly what Masseron et al. (2014) has compiled in their recent paper. Using these energy states and the calculations for the radiative and predissociative lifetimes, which are also graciously calculated by Masseron et al. (2014), we can calculate the cross sections and as well as the rate coefficient without using a specific value for the barrier, but rather implying the barrier through these values and solving from there. They calculate these lifetimes for different rotational vibrational states within the potential curve of $B^2\Sigma^-$ in nanoseconds which can be represented by τ_{pre} and τ_{rad} . These lifetimes can be converted into Γ values, which is in units of energy, and from this form we can use the equation for the cross section proposed by Bain and Bardsley (1972).

Cross Section Equation

$$\sigma_i(E) = \frac{\pi}{2ME}(2J_i + 1) \frac{\Gamma_{ri}\Gamma_{di}}{(E - E_i)^2 + \Gamma_i^2/4} \quad (1)$$

This equation for the cross section ($\sigma_i(E)$) is influenced most by the Γ_{ri} and Γ_{di} which are the radiative and predissociation energies respectively. Also the energy level E_i is important in determining where the equation will establish resonance. The E is the energy of the incoming atoms and thus is the independent variable in this equation. Some other aspects of this equation include the reduced mass of the resulting molecule M and the level of the rotational state J_i . Γ_i is the full energy of both the radiative and dissociative energies at each state, which can be represented by $\Gamma_i = \Gamma_{di} + \Gamma_{ri}$.

The value of the cross section is in atomic units (a_0^2) and all the other parts of the equation are also kept or converted into atomic units. It is possible to use the cross section to determine the rate coefficient after averaging over a Maxwellian distribution of relative velocities of the carbon and hydrogen atoms. This is one way of finding the rate coefficient, but Bain and Bardsley (1972) provided another equation using many of the same terms as the equation for the cross section which can be used to find the rate coefficients without having to bring in calculations for the relative velocities.

Rate Equation

$$\alpha_i^{res} = \left(\frac{2\pi}{MkT}\right)^{\frac{3}{2}}(2J_i + 1)\frac{\Gamma_{ri}\Gamma_{di}}{\Gamma_i}e^{\frac{-E}{kT}} \quad (2)$$

Using Γ_{ri} and Γ_{di} as well the measurements for the energies in the pertinent energy levels we can find the rate coefficient and how it varies with temperature. The energy levels of the states are very influential in this equation which produces some interesting interactions if the energy states correspond with the edge of the temperature curve.

2.2. Methods

So the method behind working with and modeling this data was very heavily based in python programming. We were able to take large blocks of data through python and convert and feed them through different codes to get graphs and numbers. Using this we were able to model the cross section against energy but have the energy be represented by kelvin so that the graph could be more easily understood in natural terms by being able to compare it to actual temperature gradients.

An important point to note is that we omitted all energy levels in both vibrational level $v=0$ and $v=1$ that feel below the base incoming energy for the atoms because the possibility of dissociation at these levels are negligibly small and the barrier has no effect below this energy. We zeroed our energies by this energy and only used states above it, which ended up

being a different amount of states for each vibrational level due the different levels in each vibrational state.

When graphing total cross section and total rate coefficient models, we added together all of the models from each J value from both $V=0$ and $V=1$ vibrational states to get a collective rate and cross section for each temperature. Using this final combined result we are able to determine the rate coefficient for this reaction.

3. Discussion

After applying the cross sectional equation from Bain and Bardsley (1972) we were able determine a cross section and rate coefficient for each energy level, both rotational and vibrational, we also were able to view how this value changes with temperature, or in the case of the cross section, with energy but in units of Kelvin so it can be understood from a relative perspective.

These are the graphs of the cross section with respect to energy for the $V=0$ and $V=1$ vibrational states from 0 to 3000 K in energy. You can see depicted in these graph several cusps or spikes in the data. These spikes are indicators of the resonances. They match with the energy of the rotational states within each vibrational layer.

Another key aspect of these graphs is the general plot trends such as the sharp rise at very low energies due to the energy factor on the bottom becoming very small. A similarly visible trend which appears more on the $V=1$ vibrational plot is the decrease in cross section as the energy increases which is due to higher energetics and can be thought of as the atoms increased energy as its own barrier to the radiative recombination.

Fig. 2.— A graph of the cross section combined from all vibrational and rotational states to get the overall rate for the interaction as a function of temperature.

The two smaller graphs above are the models of the rate coefficient for the carbon and hydrogen reaction for the $V=0$ and $V=1$ vibrational states respectively. The two graphs though look very different and if you look at Fig. 3 on the next page you can see that the increase at low temperature takes a predominant role in determining the final rate coefficient. The nature of all of the rate coefficient graphs except for one (as seen in the appendix) drop off quite drastically as the temperature approaches its low point, but this is not true for the $J=6$ rotational state in the $V=1$ vibrational state. This particular energy level falls very close to what we zeroed the energy to and this has a large effect on the rate coefficient at low temperatures. This effect is due to the resonance and could be an instance of a highly elusive threshold resonance. This pattern could also be due to the slightest of errors in the data since the threshold resonance appears at such a small fraction away from the zero. Another

Fig. 3.— A graph of the rate combined from all vibrational and rotational states to get the overall rate for the interaction as a function of temperature.

thing to consider when looking at this interesting effect in the model of the rate coefficient is that at the temperatures where this phenomena is appearing we do have to consider the fine-structure of both the molecule and the two atoms as they interact. A deeper look into this occurrence would be necessary to verify any sort of threshold resonance in this system.

As it is though we have a resulting rate of about $5 * 10^{-18} \text{cm}^3/\text{s}$ at 100 Kelvin. Like the cross section graph we can see some general trends in the rate coefficient models. Consistently, the rate falls off slowly as the temperature increases, which can be explained by the higher energies and faster velocities that the atoms would have in this temperature range and how this energy would make the time available for the two atoms to radiatively combine much shorter. This also follows why the trend rises towards the low temperature, but in most of the graphs falls drastically due to a lack of sufficient energy at that temperature to cause a radiative combination. Also the barrier comes back into play when considering the location of this steep drop off, but in the case of a threshold resonance, the favorable nature of that state overcomes the opposition of the barrier.

It is important to note that through this information I am certain it is possible to extract the height of the barrier, though through this process we have not made that our priority, but rather that we could pinpoint the rate coefficient without the exact information about the barrier. This has been accomplished and with a temperature range that is 10x larger than that of what KIDA currently has on the reaction.

Finally, there is the consideration that the rate coefficient is weighted by the probability that atoms actually approach and form the B $^2\Sigma^-$ electronic state. There are 18 possible initial states for C (3P) and H (2S), corresponding to the 9 states of the C (3P) atom and the 2 states of the H (2S) atom. Of these, 2 result in the B electronic state. So, the rate coefficient should be multiplied by the factor $g = 2/18 = 1/9$, which gives the probability of a collision into the B electronic state to be $1/9$ of the full rate coefficient that was calculated. This leaves us with an even lower coefficient of $5 * 10^{-19} \text{cm}^3/\text{s}$, but with the consideration of how adverse the effects of the barrier should be on the rate, this more precise solution seems to fit within agreeable parameters.

4. Looking Forward

The first success in the discovery of the rate coefficient of CH is that the process used through Bain and Bardsley (1972) is a viable calculation of the rate coefficient and cross section for atom to molecule interactions that have any sort of barrier involved. This could lead to further studies about reactions that had previously been left unsolved due to fine quantum mechanical uncertainties that could not be accounted for within the equation. Also now a precedent for revisiting previous reactions that were "discovered" years ago and reevaluating the precision of those calculations in favor of having complete and up to date records of chemical rate coefficients.

Other than taking this method and expounding it into other media, we now can use this rate coefficient to unravel chemical environments in space and certainly here on earth, more accurately. There has been mentions that a rate coefficient of this nature for methylidyne radical (CH) could be useful in the progress of understanding Mars and Jupiter's moon Titan. This such as planetary disks, exoplanets and their atmospheres as well as diffuse interstellar medium could be affected by these new calculations, which could help in the onslaught of new chemical information about molecules and how they might interact in a cold and sparsely populated environment.

The next level that this project could be taken to in terms of a search for a deeper understanding lies within the fine structure excitation of C by impact with H Abrahamsson et al. (2007). It would also be interesting to continue to study how the extremely low temperature interactions could be effected by the threshold effects to the rate coefficient due to a key resonance at low temperature. Just by fine tuning and making corrections using past and present we have opened many doors that could lead to new horizons.

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5. Plot Appendix

The following plots are the Cross Section Diagrams for the rotational states J=14 through J=21 at the vibrational level of V=0 in order from left to right and down.

This next set of graphs are the Cross Section depending on temperature for the V=1 vibrational state for the rotational states J=6 through J=12.

The following set of graphs are the rate versus the temperature found in the $V=0$ vibrational state in the range of the rotational levels from $J=14$ to $J=21$

The graphs below are representing the rate in respect to temperature found in the $V=1$ vibrational state in the rotational states from $J=6$ to $J=12$.

